

SUGGESTION OF A MODEL OF A CENTRALIZED SYSTEM FOR PROVIDING SERVICES IN THE FIELD OF CLINICAL TRIALS ON DRUG

Stamenovic¹, Suzana Pavlovic²

¹Pierrel Research, m.stamenovic@rocketmail.com

²Health Sanitary School of Professional Studies Visan, miskos@verat.net

Abstract: *This paper deals with the problems of current decision-making system in the field of clinical trials in Republic of Serbia and with a suggestion of implementation of proposal of innovative project management model of a centralized decision-making system in clinical trials. The current decision-making model in clinical trials in the Republic of Serbia has been observed as time consuming, expensive and non-transparent, what is burdening the sponsors of clinical trials, the institutions that conduct clinical trials as well as the participants of the trials. Contrary to this divided and localized system of the management process of clinical trials, in some EU countries appears that a centralized and more efficient system for providing services in decision-making processes in the area of clinical drug trials is possible, and it makes a contribution to the quality of the whole process. Research demonstrated in this paper has value for Ministry of Health of Republic of Serbia, Medicines and Medical Devices Agency of Serbia, Local Ethics Committees of Investigational Institutions within Serbia and international and domestic Pharmaceutical Companies and Contract research organizations involved in clinical trials processes in Serbia.*

Keywords: *health care management, clinical trials on drugs, innovation, new service development model, decision-making processes*

1. INTRODUCTION

A clinical trial is a study performed on humans with the aim to establish or confirm the clinical, pharmacological and pharmacodynamic effects of one or more drugs tested, to identify any adverse reactions to one or more tested drugs. It has for its aim to examine the absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion of one or more drugs, as well as to determine safety and efficiency of the drug (*The Official Gazette of RS, 2010*).

A sponsor of a clinical trial can be a producer, a legal or a natural person (hereinafter referred to as the sponsor) and is responsible for the initiation, management, quality and financing of the clinical trial. The sponsor may transfer some or all obligations related to the conduct of clinical trial to a Contract Research Organization located in the Republic of Serbia (hereinafter referred to as RS), which is responsible for the activities that the sponsor had transferred onto them in the process of approval and conduct of clinical trials on the territory of RS.

The sponsor is responsible for the activities transferred to the Contract Research Organization (*The Official Gazette of RS, 2010*). Prior to the beginning of clinical trials, the Local Ethics Committee of the Research Institution makes a decision on the conduct of the clinical trial (*The Official Gazette of RS, 2010*).

The Ethics Committee considers the request for conducting the clinical trial with documentation submitted and brings a decision within 60 days from establishing that the application is complete (*The Official Gazette of RS, 2010*). The Ethics Committee is obliged to inform the sponsor of the clinical trial or authorized Contract Research Organization as well as the Medicines and Medical Devices Agency of Serbia (hereinafter ALIMS) about its decision within 15 days (*The Official Gazette of RS, 2010*). If the Ethics Committee does not make a positive decision on conducting the clinical trial, ALIMS will not issue the authorization of clinical trials.

The approval for the new clinical trials on drug/drugs implies that the sponsor of the clinical trial, who does not have an approval for the drug in RS, or the drug proposed to be used, must apply for the authorization of clinical trials and submit to ALIMS complete documentation in conformity with the law and regulations. The sponsor submits the documentation that includes: a summary of the nature and characteristics of the drug, conducted research in order to define its pharmacological and toxicological properties, clinical experience, the protocol of proposed trial, a list of all researchers and institutions involved in the study, as well as the

approval of all Local Ethics Committees of the Research Institutions (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010). The content of the request i.e. documents necessary for the authorization of the clinical trial, as well as the protocol of the clinical trial, is prescribed by the Minister in charge of health affairs (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010). If all the requirements stipulated in this law and regulations adopted in order to implement this law are met, ALIMs will issue the authorization to conduct the clinical trial (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010).

In the RS the decision-making in the field of clinical trials is conducted in several phases, which are long, segmented, and with an uncertain outcome. The basic problem in the decision-making system - the department of service provided by state institutions in the field of clinical trials - appears to be in localization and segmentation of certain phases of the service in the decision-making system. Based on EU Directive 2001/20/EC, it is possible to implement various decision-making models in this field. Ministry of Health of the RS through ALIMs implements a system in Serbia that includes the decision-making structure during the authorization of clinical trials or the authorization of variations of and amendments to clinical trials provided in the graphic (Figure 1). Funding for the entire decision-making process is provided by the sponsor of the clinical trials. The sponsor of the clinical trial on drug/drugs pays the appropriate sum of money for the services received from the Local Ethics Committee and the ALIMs. The amount of money paid for the services completed is in accordance with the statutes of these institutions, and is paid as a compensation for the bringing of the appropriate decision according to the conclusion of the meeting of the expert committee and submitted documents of the clinical trials on drug/drugs.

The time component in terms of the length of the entire decision-making process is of great importance for to the sponsor of the clinical trial as well as for the researchers and patients (i.e. potential users of the drug being tested). In divided and localized decision-making system, the changes of the expected deadlines are frequent and endless. It should be noted that in this paper the decision-making process is being reviewed at its most important and most complex processes within the clinical trials related to institutional decision-making systems such as obtaining the authorization of clinical trials in the RS and obtaining the authorization of variations of and amendments to clinical trials.

The model from the graphic (Figure 2), of a centralized innovative decision-making system for provision of services in the field of clinical trials, provides the opportunity to avoid some shortcomings in terms of time, cost and efficiency of the existing models.

The main contribution of this system would be in optimization of the decision-making within the Ethics Committees centralized at the national level. Thus, the speed of decision-making would be greater, the chances to delay the process would be smaller and, ultimately the cost of the process would be reduced. The centralized innovative decision-making system enables the concentration of certain parts of decision - making. At the same time the proposed model would reduce the number of procedural and administrative processes in each institution and thereby it would reduce the cost and increase the efficiency.

2. THE EXISTING SYSTEM FOR PROVIDING SERVICES WITHIN THE DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES IN THE FIELD OF CLINICAL TRIALS

As part of this paper, the current system for providing services within the decision-making in the field of clinical trials, based on the existing legislation, is presented (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010). The process presented (Figure 1) considers a situation in which the sponsor of the clinical trial requests for the services in the form of an authorization for conducting clinical trials or requests the authorization of variations of and amendments to clinical trials. These two procedures are considered as the most complex requests in which we can see the most clearly the decision-making process in Serbia.

The system is managed by the highest authority, the Ministry of Health of the RS, through the ALIMS. The set system can be modified only in case of changes of relevant legislation relating to the existing procedures.

Figure 1: The current system of providing services in decision-making processes in the field of clinical trials, provided by the author

Phase I - According to the Law on medicines and medical devices of RS the sponsor of the clinical trial is required to submit all necessary documents to the decisions-making system within RS for assessment in order to obtain the authorization of clinical trials in RS or to obtain the authorization of variations of and amendments to the already authorized clinical trial on the territory of RS (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010). The sponsor of the clinical trial on drug/drugs e.g. a pharmaceutical company that wants to implement a certain stage of scientific trial on the territory of the RS, authorizes a Contract Research Organization (CRO) to apply for the conduct or variations within the clinical trial (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010). In the above mentioned graphic (Figure 1) the sponsor authorized the Contract Research Organization to submit the appropriate documents to the state institutions.

Phase II - The Contract Research Organization (CRO) is authorized by the sponsor of clinical trial (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010). Based on the contract between the Contract Research Organization and the sponsor, the Contract Research Organization has the authority to submit all legally stipulated documents to the authorities of the state responsible for the decision-making process related to clinical trials. In the case of the mentioned existing model in the RS, as shown in the graph (Figure 1), the institutions to which documents are being submitted to are Research Institutions, Local Ethics Committees of Research Institutions and the ALIMS, in the given order. In this step the necessary documents e.g. contracts, consents of the responsible persons, etc. should be submitted to Research Institutions and based on those documents the Contract Research Organization is able to move to the phase III. This phase includes the submitting of all documents related to the clinical trial of a medicinal product together with the documents

received from the Research Institutions of Local Ethics Committees. When the paid service is obtained in the form of approval of the Local Ethics Committees, that approval and all the documents are further submitted to ALIMS whose services are paid additionally, depending on the type of service.

Phase III - The graphic (Figure 1) shows three Local Ethics Committees of Research Institutions and the fourth is shown as the n^t (there can be a maximum number within the number of existing clinical centers and medical centers in the RS, because each of them represents a potential research center for specific therapeutic indications (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010)). We can state that the number of 4-8 Research Institutions makes an average number of institutions participating in a clinical trial, and therefore the number of Local Ethics Committees that make decisions on clinical trials is 4-8 - each Research Institution has its own locally organized ethics committee that provides services in the decision-making process (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010). The Contract Research Organization (CRO) has the obligation to submit all the documents received from the sponsor (adjusted to the local laws of the RS) to the Local Ethics Committees under whose approval it may proceed with the process of submitting documents to higher instances (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010). In the case of RS the higher instance for decision-making is the ALIMS. The Local Ethics Committees provide services related to appropriate decision-making according to specific demands of clinical trials on drug/drugs. They are being paid for their services by sponsors of clinical trials through the Contract Research Organization (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010).

Phase IV - shows the step in which the Contract Research Organization takes over the decisions made by Local Ethics Committees and with further adaptation processes submits the overall documentation received from the sponsor, together with the approvals obtained from the Local Ethic Committees to the ALIMS (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010).

Phase V - shows the step in which the documents are being delivered to ALIMS - (Competent Authority), and then within the legal deadline, depending on the service requested, final approval issued by the Ministry of Health of the RS is expected (*The Official Gazette* of RS, 2010).

Phases III and V, present the submission of documents by the authorized Contract Research Organization to the state authorities paid as a service provided by the state institutions in the name of provision of services in the area of decision making - making of appropriate decisions at the meetings of expert committees. Prices are determined by the statutes of the institutions to which the documents are submitted to. A number of institutions (committees for providing services in the decision-making process) lead to the multiplication of payments for basically the same service.

3. THE PROPOSAL OF AN INNOVATIVE CENTRALIZED SYSTEM FOR PROVIDING SERVICES IN DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES IN THE FIELD OF CLINICAL TRIALS ON DRUG / DRUGS

This section presents a proposal of a centralized system for providing services in the decision-making processes in clinical trials which is primarily based on the provision of such services on the territory of the Republic of Romania. Beside the Republic of Romania, many European countries have introduced a system for providing Centralized services in decision-making processes in the field of clinical trials (European commission, 2008.). Decision-making process itself is arranged differently from country to country and adapted to local laws. Among others, the Republic of Romania follows Directives of the European Commission 2011/20/EC, then Directive 2003/94/EC, 2005/28/EC and ICH E6, which make it one of the countries of the European Union that has fully harmonized its system with all the European and international regulations and standards (The European Forum for Good Clinical Practice, 2011). EU Clinical Trials Directive 2001/20/EC, allows the implementation of various models of the decision-making system - a department for providing clinical trials services. The system shown in the graphic (Figure 2), is primarily better due to centralized decision-making system. Within this centralization all Local Ethics Committees of Research Institutions (Figure 1, Phase III) that participate in clinical trials have created one, a National Ethics Committee, whose goal is to shorten the decision-making time and increase the quality of decision-making (Figure 2, Phase III). In the Republic of Romania (Figure 2), the National Ethics Committee for clinical trials is an independent body. National Ethics Committee is under the direct jurisdiction of the Ministry of Health of Romania (The European Forum for Good Clinical Practice, 2011).

Figure 2: The proposal of an innovative centralized system for providing services in decision-making processes in the field of clinical trials, provided by the author

In the case of the innovative system based on the examples of service provision systems in the decision-making processes within clinical trials in the Republic of Romania, the sponsor of the clinical trial would be, as in the present system of the RS, legally required to submit the documents to the Contract Research Organization. This Organization would adapt the stipulated documentation to local laws, and submit it to the National Ethics Committee, instead of numerous Local Ethics Committees of Research Institutions. In that case the multiplication of the costs, prolongation of the decision-making process and non-transparency of the decision-making process in the form of paid services to local authorities, would be avoided. All other decision-making processes and procedural systems for providing services would remain the same as in the graphic (Figure 1).

4. A MODEL OF AN INNOVATIVE CENTRALIZED SYSTEM FOR PROVIDING SERVICES IN DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES IN FIELD OF CLINICAL TRIALS OBSERVED THROUGH A PHASE MODEL OF DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE SERVICES

The innovative system for providing services focuses primarily on the formation of a new National Ethics Committee and by that a new service provider in the decision-making process would be initiated. Activities of this innovative service would lead to cost reductions and greater certainty regarding time and finances within the decision-making process. In this paper, in the aim of further implementation of the model of centralized innovative system for decision-making in clinical trials, one of the well-known innovation project models in the services, the Sashimi model, can be used. Sashimi model is so called because it features overlapping phases, like the overlapping fish of Japanese sashimi (Ward, 1998). Initially it was referred to as the "waterfall model with overlapping phases" or "the waterfall model with feedback" according to Matkovic and Tumbas (2010). Since the phases in the Sashimi model overlap, it may point to existing

problems during the implementation of the project very well. The phase model of the development of the new service could be based on this model.

4.1 The phase model of the development of the new service

According to Milutinovic and Stosic (2011), the phase development of Sashimi model includes the following overlapping phases:

1. Possibility analysis
2. Feasibility and defining
3. Design and testing
4. Development
5. Implementation and a pilot test
6. Commercialization

4.1.1 Possibility Analysis

Within this analysis it is necessary to determine if the implemented service would be profitable and thus justify its implementation. If so, it is possible to move onto the next phase. Involved organizations estimate the prospects for implementation of such project in terms of capacity and support for further implementation of this project. The final decision on implementation in this case must be made by the state, i.e. the Ministry of Health of the RS. Within the Ministry of Health, organizational changes of the new service model would include institutions of the ALIMS as well as the Local Ethics Committees within research centers i.e. clinical centers and medical centers in the RS. Their network infrastructure would have to be eligible. The purpose of the implementation of this model of the decision-making process in terms of service, when making decisions about clinical trials, primarily is to provide transparent, more efficient and less expensive process that would bring relief to all participants in this process and mostly to the sponsor of the clinical trial e.g. cost reduction, the increase in speed of the decision-making process, then to researchers e.g. increase in speed of decision-making process, and finally to our patients e.g. enabling the use of the innovative drug in a timely manner. From the state's point of view, centralized innovative decision-making would contribute to a clearer and more transparent monitoring system of clinical trials that are underway, as well as to faster and more efficient decision-making and implementing decisions on existing or anticipated clinical trials. Also, with the increase of favorable business conditions and with the convergence of current conditions to efficient and applicable models in the world, the state would provide good business conditions and thus increase the number of sponsors to whom timely decisions and pricing could be crucial in the case of selection of the country where they would conduct their research and commercial activities. The increase in the number of sponsors enables the larger number of the above mentioned studies that can contribute to creation of new workplaces in the field of innovative technologies and services, as well as greater visibility and prestige of our Research Institutions in the world, which is partially reflected through a number of published and successful clinical trials in which our researchers were the participants. The innovative centralized service provision in the decision making process in the field of clinical trials cannot be initiated prior to the changes in the statutory legal framework that would enable its implementation. The ministry is also obligated to harmonize the internal affairs with subordinate legislations within 60 days from the date of enactment of the necessary legal regulations.

4.1.2 Feasibility and defining

Within the second phase the service provider/service should be defined. Getting out of this phase would be in the form of a draft of a final service. It should be defined in detail what the service implies. In the case of the proposed implementation of the model of the centralized innovative decision-making system in clinical trials main phases are listed in the graphic (Figure 1 and Figure 2). The graphic (Figure 1) represents the current service provision system within the decision-making process in clinical trials, and the graphic (Figure 2) represents an innovative model for centralized provision of services in the process of decision-making in the field of clinical trials. As stated in the introduction, this decision-making system is best to be observed through the most complex and the most important decisions related to the clinical trials in the RS. For providing the decision-making service and for revision of the submitted documents at the meeting of the expert board of a Local Ethics Committee of a Research Institution, as well as the ALIMS, certain compensation is provided in accordance with the statutes of these institutions. Such decisions include the authorization of clinical trials and the authorization of variations of and amendments to clinical trials.

The idea to implement the innovative model is based on the restructuring the existing decision-making process and the centralization of the existing decision-making system within which the service of the

decision-making would be transferred from the level of Local Ethics Committees of Research Institutions to the centralized innovative service of the decision-making system and thus avoid multiplication of submitting documents required for decision-making, reduce decision making costs i.e. one decision-making committee would be paid instead of all local committees for making individual decisions, and it would also reduce the possibility of prolonging the bringing of appropriate approvals - according to the centralized decision-making system (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Proposal of substantial changes in the infrastructure network of the system for decision-making services from divided and localized systems into a centralized innovative system for providing decision making services in clinical trials, provided by the author

4.1.3 Design, development, implementation and pilot test

Within this phase, project should get a clear outline of the design in terms of further solving of the infrastructural problems. Declaration EU 2001/20/EC enables implementation of the innovative centralized service model for the providing services in the decision-making process in the field of clinical trials. Within this phase it is expected that all the components are included and the operational support systems are identified and defined precisely. The Ministry of Health should define a transition strategy to the innovative centralized service model for the provision of services in the decision-making process in the field of clinical trials. The design should be related to the Development of the project and it should be based on the action plan drawn up in accordance with the strategy. Given the specificity of the service that is being implemented, it is necessary to determine the position of the Central Ethics Committee i.e. National Ethics Committee, and official representative body for provision of service in the decision-making process. In order to reduce costs during the implementation, we suggest that the location of the Central Ethics Committee should be in the building of the ALIMS. In this way, the physical proximity of the two inevitable institutions in the service providing system of decision-making within clinical trials will contribute to the transparency of the service providing process. It is also necessary to establish a professional board of the Central Ethics Committee that would be responsible for providing services in decision-making in clinical trials on drug/drugs.

4.1.4 Development

The development is the phase of the model in which the infrastructure of an organization and the infrastructure of a service are combined and unified (Milutinovic&Stosic, 2011). After the planning process, the work on the infrastructural processes and the time component should be done. Ministry of Health of the RS is obliged to obtain all necessary documentation related to the implementation of the innovative centralized service for providing services in the decision-making process in the field of clinical trials.

4.1.5 Implementation and a pilot test

Serbian Ministry of Health should support all that is required within the implementation in order to carry out the listed services. The other segment is related specific testing of the innovative decision-making system in the field of the clinical trials. Within the implementation, it is necessary to analyze the very infrastructure and the needs for adapting the new services and to adjust them to enacted laws and regulations, in accordance with the desire for a more efficient service providing system in the decision making process in clinical trials.

4.1.6 Commercialization

Commercialization presents a phase of the Sashimi model which should sum all previous phases and thus ensure the readiness of the entire network for final functioning of the service in commercial purposes. The particularity of the project leads to further specificities of this phase. Namely, when a service system for decision-making in the field of clinical trials is changed once, it is not possible to proceed according to the previous decision-making system, i.e. the selection and the final implementation and commercialization of innovative system for delivering services in decision-making process in clinical trials would be a final and unique solution for all further processes of obtaining the authorization of clinical trials and obtaining the authorization of variations of and amendments to clinical trials. It follows that it is essential, before the project is finally commercialized, that all users of the innovative decision-making system in the field of clinical trials are clearly informed about the changes, as well as about and the way of functioning of the new implemented system. Therefore, it is necessary to make a separate promotion system of a new innovative model of the centralized service within the decision-making process in the field of clinical trials that would provide all end users high quality information on time. These kinds of changes are made by the Serbian Ministry of Health in *the Official Gazette of RS*. According to the Public information law, new laws on which the future innovative system is based on will come into force eight days after its publication in *the Official Gazette of RS*.

5. CONCLUSION

Modern decision-making systems require optimization of resources and time. The present model is shown to be insufficiently flexible for various requirements of the pharmaceutical industry. In the RS, the decision-making system in the field of the authorization of clinical trials and the authorization of variations of and amendments to clinical trials is being conducted in several phases, which are long, segmented, and with an uncertain outcome. The main problem in the field of clinical trials, related to the decision making process, occurs precisely in the localization and division of certain phases of the service within the system of decision-making. Based on EU Directive 2001/20/EC the use of various decision-making models in this area is possible and the proposal of the model for implementation presented in this paper (Figure 2) would allow a significant improvement in the speed of decisions-making, or in terms of transparency and further cost reductions. Such services provided by the state and paid by foreign investors, in this case the sponsors of clinical trials, must be highly efficient and advanced to ensure the satisfaction of the end users of the mentioned services in order to fully optimize quality and time components. In a time of growing competition, we can say that every innovation in terms of service that enables optimization of resources represents a comparative advantage in relation to the countries that do not have such services. The investors who are satisfied with the clear and pragmatic solutions in the decision-making system in the field of clinical trials will be happy to re-engage in scientific research and commercial activity on the territory of RS. The benefits are multiple.

In this paper the proposed model of managing innovation projects in the area of new technical services is used. Based on the specifics of the innovative system, there are certain characteristics in the application of the Sashimi model. On the basis of adaptation according to the specifics of the innovative project for providing services in decision-making process in the field of clinical trials, Sashimi phase model of development of new service can be applied to this subject. Also, it should be noted that the phases of the Sashimi model may need further segmentation. Of great importance for the implementation of this innovative system is also legal - political framework, without which it is absolutely impossible to go into the process of changing the existing model. Experts need to initiate the process of changes on the basis of the evident shortcomings of the existing system, and the state should recognize further potential of the planned innovation projects. Also, the strategy and action plan should be done and in this way enable the implementation of the project. Considering the above mentioned, it can be concluded that during the development and implementation of new service the local environment must be taken into consideration, so that the phase model of the development of the new service could be applied in the right way.

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